

PROSPECTS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAT CLUSTERS IN FOOD SAFETY

Jamshid Sharafetdinovich Tukhtabaev

PhD., Associate Professor, “Economic security” department, Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan,

E-mail:jamshidtukhtabaev@gmail.com

Erkin Xayitovich Botirov

PhD., Associate Professor, “Agroeconomics” department, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan. E-mail:ebotirov1967@gmail.com

Numon Xasanov

PhD., Associate Professor, “Agroeconomics” department, Tashkent state agrarian university, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan, E-mail:numanxasanov@gmail.com

Khusniddin Fakhriddinovich Uktamov

Head teacher at “Economic security” Department, Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan,

E-mail:husniddin1309@gmail.com

Sherzod Ermatovich Yuldashev

Assistant of the Department of "Food and Agricultural Economics", Samarkand branch of Tashkent State University of Economics

E-mail:sher.yuldashev22@gmail.com

Imron Ilhomovich Rakhimov

Assistant at “Economic security” department, Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan, E-mail:imron.rakh@gmail.com

Abstract: This article outlines the prospects for the establishment and development of oil and gas clusters in agriculture. Also, agricultural and industrial enterprises producing oilseeds from oilseeds were studied and analyzed. Scientific-theoretical and methodological-practical solutions to the problems of production cooperation of agricultural and industrial enterprises. The experience of foreign countries on the relationship between the formation of agro-cluster policy in the regions of Uzbekistan and the mechanism of economic relations between cluster participants was studied. Execution of contracts between JSC "Kason Oil-Extraction" of Kashkadarya region and farms for the cultivation of sugarcane and the implementation of the contract between JSC "Kason Oil-Extraction" of Kashkadarya region and farmers for the supply of seeds of cedar. A survey was conducted to study the problems in the activities of enterprises growing and processing oilseeds, and a fat agro-cluster was proposed in Kashkadarya region. Conclusions and proposals have been developed to support and develop the production of oil and fat products in Kashkadarya region.

Keywords: agriculture, oil and oil clusters, oilseeds, industrial enterprises, JSC "Kasan oil and extraction", farms, processing enterprises, agro-clusters, oil products.

Introduction

As a result of consistent reforms in recent years to modernize and diversify agricultural production, to develop the processing industry, a new system of activity in the agricultural sector - the cluster method has been introduced. At the same time, there are no effective mechanisms for coordinating the activities of cotton and textile clusters, overcoming systemic problems in their activities and protecting their interests in public administration.

At present, there are mutual economic relations based on bilateral agreements between agriculture and industrial enterprises producing oilseeds from oilseeds. Oilseeds and small enterprises purchase oilseeds and cottonseed as primary raw materials from farms and other agricultural organizations. Thus, there are stages of mutual cooperation in the production of vegetable oil based on agreements between three-stage producers of raw materials, processing enterprises and trade organizations.

However, while such contractual relations are based on the requirements of market relations, they do not fully comply with the principles of long-term mutually beneficial cooperation. As a result, the requirements of contracts related to the quantity and quality of raw materials are not always met. The existence of these cases is confirmed by the analysis of contracts with farmers for the purchase of grain "Karshi Oil Extraction Plant" and "Kasan Oil Extraction Plant". At the same time, the increase in the cost of raw materials leads to higher consumer prices for wholesale and retail oil products. It should be noted that "cluster strategies" have become more popular in foreign countries in recent years [1]. Clusters were created in the practical centers of entrepreneurship, which were able to demonstrate their strength and competitiveness in the global market. The state supports existing clusters and supports the creation of new ones that were not previously related to each other. The cluster strategy is widely used in European countries. For example, in Germany, since 1995, the program for the creation of biotechnological clusters Bio Regio has been launched. In the UK, the government has designated Edinburgh, around Oxford and Southeast England as important areas for the placement of biotechnology

firms. In Norway, the government encourages cooperation between firms in the “maritime” cluster. In Finland, a large-scale study entitled “Advantage Finland-The Future of Finnish Industries” was launched in 1995 to identify cluster development trends and assess competitive prospects. The Finnish Institute for Economic Research (ETLA) has identified nine major clusters: information and telecommunications, metallurgy, energy, business services, healthcare, machinery, food and construction”[2]. The close cooperation in the dissemination of knowledge between the firms of these clusters will ensure a competitive advantage over their main competitors. It also leads the country in both research and technology cooperation. With this in mind, the main goal of the state cluster policy at this stage is to create conditions for increasing the level of competitiveness of the agro-industrial complex through the introduction of a cluster model of development. To this end, the following objectives of agro-cluster policy should be identified [3]:

- formation of the regulatory framework governing the activities of agro-clusters in the field of development;
- setting priorities for the formation and development of agro-clusters and monitoring in the field of agricultural cluster development;
- creation of conditions for professional training of specialists and managers on the development of agro-clusters;
- creating conditions for the development and implementation of agro-cluster initiatives and projects;
- formation of a system of state support for the cluster model of agricultural development and ensuring its functioning.

The Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan should provide assistance in the formation of innovative agro-industrial clusters by government agencies. It is necessary to plan the formation of cluster initiatives in the agricultural sector, as well as the formation of small businesses and private entrepreneurs interested in the further implementation of cluster projects. To do this, it is necessary to create a favorable institutional environment in the field of cluster development of the economy [4].

The centralization of state efforts to introduce a cluster model of development, taking into account the world experience in improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, should include the following areas of state cluster policy [5]:

- regulatory and legal regulation of activities in the field of cluster development of the economy, including the development and adoption of draft regulations on the cluster development of the national economy (national technological platforms, innovation complexes, cluster associations, strategic unions, etc.)), as well as government support measures in the implementation of cluster projects;
- organization and implementation of continuous monitoring of the processes of formation and development of clusters on the basis of small business and private entrepreneurship, including the establishment of priorities for their development across the region. It is also required to develop guidelines for the organization and implementation of monitoring of cluster development of the economy, reflecting the issues of organization and identification of clusters formed on the basis of small business and private entrepreneurship;

- organizational and methodological support in the development and implementation of cluster initiatives and projects. To this end, it is planned to establish social advisory councils and commissions under the Ministry of Economy and Industry, the Ministry of Innovation Development and the authorities, including representatives of the business community, science and education interested in the implementation of cluster initiatives and projects;
- support self-organization of small business and private entrepreneurship in the formation of clusters, including the development and promotion of cluster initiatives in the implementation of future cluster projects.

Establishment and operation of agro-cluster development centers in the regions can be carried out in the following areas [6]:

- support cluster projects through the provision of organizational, information and analytical services to cluster participants;
- consulting services (legal, financial, engineering and other services);
- search for additional sources to finance the implementation of cluster projects;
- development of business plans;
- marketing research;
- promotion of products of cluster participants;
- organization of conferences, seminars and other information events for cluster participants;
- organization of training and advanced training of management and specialist staff of cluster participants;
- Creation and organization of industrial sites in the regions for the organization of production and sale of goods (works, services) by small business and private entrepreneurship as a basis for the formation of innovative industrial clusters of small business and private entrepreneurship;
- organization of training and advanced training of managers and specialists on the development and implementation of cluster projects. In this regard, it is planned to identify basic organizations that provide educational services in the field of cluster development of the agricultural sector;
- organization of information and explanatory work on the prospects of using the cluster model of agricultural development. This requires information and educational activities for government agencies and business representatives with the participation of foreign experts on cluster development of the economy, including the study of practical experience in initiating and implementing specific cluster projects.

At present, it is expedient to ensure the formation of agroclusters in two different organizational forms [7]:

- organization of agro-cluster participants in a number of areas (marketing research, organization and conduct of joint research and development and innovative projects, implementation of information-educational and advertising activities, construction and (or) operation of public facilities; etc.) to conclude a simple cooperation agreement (agreement on joint activities) in which the coordinated activities are carried out in the interests of all participants of the cluster. In this case, a cluster council will be formed from the participants' leaders, but no special apparatus will be established to perform the functions of the cluster development center;

- creation by agro-cluster participants of a separate legal entity outside the cluster council or transfer of functions to the existing organization, which is a cluster development organization. A cluster development organization can be established in the form of an agroholding society.

The organization, which initiated the development of the agro-cluster, should be entrusted with the following functions [8]:

- organization of interaction of cluster participants and ensuring the legal rights and common interests of cluster participants in relations with government agencies;
- development of cluster projects and organization of their implementation;
- organization of management and operation of cluster specialized infrastructure in the interests of all participants of the cluster.

Thus, the cluster development organization is represented as a management company for cluster development, which ensures the implementation of the decisions of the agro-cluster council, as well as the organization of the implementation of cluster projects.

Analysis of the relevant literature

Scientific-theoretical and methodological-practical solutions to the problems of production cooperation of agricultural and industrial enterprises Scientists of the CIS countries V.V Kazarezov, K.V Kopach, V.V Miloserdov, A.N Rasskazov, A.V Tkach, It is reflected in the scientific works of M.I. Tugan-Baranovsky, A.V. Chayanov, GISHmelev and others [9,10].

In turn, the work of economists of our country also contributes to the study of this problem. In particular, B.B.Berkinov, I.Murodov, R.H.Toshmatov, O.P.Umurzakov, N.S.Khushmatov, Q.A.Choriev, T.X.Farmonov, T.Farmonov, Sh.D. Ergashkhodjaeva and other economists [11,12,13]. However, in our opinion, despite the immense role and importance of agricultural enterprises in the country's economy, the scope of knowledge about the direct and indirect production cooperation in their activities is very narrow. and research on the activities of industrial enterprises processing agricultural raw materials related to production cooperation is insufficient. At the same time, high consumer prices for oilseeds, as well as losses before the processing of oilseeds and rising transaction costs in the processing industry, currently lead to a low level of cooperation.

The scientific methodological and practical principles and mechanisms of this process are widely substantiated in the research of Professor K.A Choriev [14]. The author identifies the main priorities for the development of cooperation in the agricultural sector of the country. The author also stressed the expediency of the formation of agricultural cooperatives in the sheep joint of vertical integration. Therefore, in his research, the author developed the organizational structure of agricultural cooperation and the composition of its divisions. On this basis, the stages of formation of the cooperative, the mechanisms of organization and regulation of economic and financial relations of its divisions, as well as the sources of their effectiveness are indicated.

In our opinion, on the basis of the principles and methods justified by Professor K.A Choriev, the consolidation of mutually beneficial cooperation between farmers and other agricultural producers and service farms and the organization of their management structure at the district, regional and national levels , as well as accelerates the introduction of production cooperation with infrastructure enterprises [15].

As noted above, the participation of farms in industrial cooperation as small business entities largely depends on their production specialization. For example, it specializes in the sale and purchase of raw materials (at the district level) with the existing cotton industry and grain processing enterprises, which exist in the areas of farms specializing in the production of cotton and grain. However, they do not enter into cooperation in the production of mutually beneficial, voluntary end products. In this regard, the scientific work of B.B. Berkinov, M.A Aynakulov, OT Jumaev has a methodological significance in the organization and evaluation of the effectiveness of agro-industrial cooperation [16]. The research of B.B. Berkinov and M.A. Aynakulov is based on the main factors that form the basis of cooperation between small and large processing enterprises in the region, its legal norms and criteria for the distribution of income (profit) among members of the cooperative. The work of these authors is based on a system of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of vertical cooperation and integration of networks and ways to improve it [17].

O.T Jumaev's research in this area is devoted to the problems of organization and development of cooperation processes in the fruit and vegetable complex [18]. In the research work of the author the mechanism of the organization and carrying out of mutual cooperation of the enterprises of fruit and vegetable complex on the basis of scientific generalization of foreign experience is substantiated. The need to expand cooperation in the field and the prospects for the development of horizontal cooperation in the fruit and vegetable sector were suggested.

Research methodology

In our opinion, the implementation of cluster policy should be initiated by the regional public administration bodies, the cluster development organization and the cluster management bodies. This ensures a balance of interests between businesses, science and government. Therefore, the objectives of the formation of regional agro-cluster policy should be as follows (Table 1).

Table 1

Formation of agro-cluster policy in the regions of Uzbekistan

№	Name	Contents
1.	Ensuring diversification of the regional economy and high economic growth rates	By increasing the competitiveness and strengthening their export potential of enterprises, suppliers of equipment and components, specialized production and service providers, research and educational organizations that make up the regional agro-industrial clusters
2.	Stimulating development	Development of innovative potential and innovative infrastructure elements of the region within the opportunities of cluster approach
3.	Acceleration of public-private partnership mechanisms	By forming a framework for joint action by representatives of government agencies, local governments, business, education and public organizations
4.	Intensification of investment attraction and enterprise integration	The structure of the cluster includes the regional, national and international levels of the economy

processes

Based on the identification of promising types of goods, the analysis of their share in the export of products among the types of promising products produced by agricultural enterprises in the region (ie Kashkadarya region) [19]:

- medium and long-term forecasting of the volume and price dynamics of competitive agricultural products;
- to determine the efficiency of enterprises capable of forming a cluster core (production of promising products);
- identification of resources required for cluster development. The level of availability of raw materials, financial resources, production capacity, etc. of enterprises producing promising products located within Kashkadarya region is analyzed;
- Analysis of existing opportunities to create the missing elements of the infrastructure for agrocluster activities;
- Determining the level of cooperation of key participants of the agro-cluster (manufacturers, suppliers), the level of cooperation of potential participants of the agro-cluster on the basis of a survey among the heads of promising enterprises.

There are three systems of individual strengthening of agrocluster participants [20]:

- This system of administrative coercion does not correspond to the conditions of a market economy;
- The most important employee incentive system. Such a reinforcement system allows to motivate only a certain part of the staff, not to involve the rest in the integration process;
- Incentive schemes for active organizational work, rewards (high competition for the job), clear individual performance indicators, openness, achievements, ideas for improving performance.

Thus, the most important thing is not only to assess the potential for the development of the region, ie Kashkadarya region in a cluster (especially oil and gas cluster), but also to improve its institutional framework.

It is known that in the Strategy of actions on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 [21]:

- “Ensuring comprehensive and effective use of natural, mineral resources, industry, agriculture, tourism and labor potential of each region to accelerate socio-economic development, increase living standards and incomes;
- expanding the scale of modernization and diversification of the regional economy, reducing the gaps in the level of socio-economic development of the regions through the rapid development of relatively low-growth districts and cities, primarily through increasing industrial and export potential;
- Accelerated development of small towns and settlements through the establishment of new industrial enterprises and service centers, the creation of small industrial zones, the attraction of funds of large business associations, bank loans and private foreign investment;

- reduction of subsidy-dependent districts and cities and expansion of the revenue base of local budgets through the rapid development of industry and services;
- further development and modernization of production, engineering, communication and social infrastructure of the regions in order to create favorable conditions for the location of industrial enterprises and other production facilities, the development of private entrepreneurship and improving the living conditions of the population.

In order to effectively fulfill these tasks, the issue of widespread introduction in our country of a cluster mechanism, which is widely used in world practice and gives its results, is relevant today [22].

For example, in the United States, there is almost no clear national policy aimed at cluster development. The state only uses traditional supports such as competition, support for research and education activities. The main initiators of cluster development policy are the regions (states and other small administrative regions). In the United States, the federal government does not have the authority to directly interfere in the policy pursued by regional territorial clusters. In turn, the U.S. Federal government agencies, such as the Economic Development Administration (EDA), which operates under the Department of Commerce (DoC) (USA), work with regional economic development and direct regions, and support the use of a cluster approach in developing regional socio-economic development strategies [23].

In this regard, the French government has been implementing a national cluster policy since 2005. Interaction with the local government plays an important role in this process [24].

In Germany, clusters have long developed without government intervention, but in 2003 the central government introduced a number of programs to support individual regions and sectors. Cluster structures draw financial resources from federal and local sources. It should be noted that these state-owned companies will receive tax benefits if they implement innovative projects, otherwise they will not receive anything or will be subject to large fines [25].

Foreign experience shows that in the developed countries of North America and Western Europe, the policy of clustering is carried out on a "bottom-up" system, ie from the regional to the state (federal) level. In Russia, by contrast, central governments take the initiative to develop clusters, while local governments adapt their programs and strategies to federally adopted programs and strategies [26].

We can observe a similar situation in our country. Therefore, it is expedient to develop a law regulating the formation and development of cluster structures so that local governments and economic entities operating in the region understand the mechanism of cluster operation and the relationship, rights and interests, responsibilities, opportunities and benefits of all participants. This law can be conditionally called the law "On the formation of cluster structures in Uzbekistan." The main feature of this legal and regulatory document is the regulation of all components and elements to support clusters in the regions of the country. In our opinion, the law "On the formation of cluster structures in Uzbekistan" should consist of the following sections [27]:

1. Subject and purpose of regulation of this law.
2. Legal regulation of relations arising in the formation of cluster structures. In this section, in our opinion, the organizational and legal form of enterprises and organizations included in the

cluster, the order of registration; tax accounting, activity control and reporting; it is expedient to shed light on legal issues such as the elimination of elements of cluster structures and their consequences.

3. Reflection of the basic concepts and principles of clusters in the law:

- A clear definition of the concept of "cluster";
- cluster criteria;
- composition of subjects;
- goals and objectives of the activity;
- stages of classification and development.

Analysis and results

Production of cotton and vegetable oil in Kashkadarya region is carried out on the basis of contracts between enterprises and growers of cotton and oilseeds (mainly farms). For each contract, an advance (seed) and seeds are allocated to farms at the rate of 30% of the amount specified in the contract. But, unfortunately, farms are not able to supply not only the amount of raw materials agreed in the contract, but also for the amount of raw materials provided. As a result, illegal behavior occurs between the processing enterprise and the farm. This situation has led to many lawsuits against farms in recent years, for which the processing company has to pay large transaction (contract) costs, such as state fees and postage. After the complaints are considered in court, employees who go to the districts will be mobilized to get the money back from the farms. This situation also results in certain contract costs [28].

Farms are not able to return the advance money received in advance, or such cases are caused by their false concealment of the harvest. They are interested in selling their products at a higher price than the contract price set in the market, rather than the enterprise, in violation of the terms of the contract. These cases lead to additional contractual costs for JSC "Kasan Oil Extraction" for non-compliance with the terms of a large number of contracts resulting from illegal actions (Table 2). The data in this table show that the company has signed contracts with 60 farms operating in the region. According to the agreement between the enterprise and the farms, the farms did not fully fulfill their obligations to cultivate molasses [29].

Table 2

Execution of contractual agreements between JSC "Kasan Oil Extraction" Kashkadarya region and farms on the cultivation of cedar (2019)

№	Districts	Number of farms	Crop area, ga			Gross yield, t			The amount of beans, mln. sum		
			режа	хақ.	фарқ, %	режа	хақ.	фарқ, %	Режа	хақ.	фарқ, %
1	Yakkabog	18	2000	2000	100	1000	1000	100	3,3	0,6	1,8

2	Shahrisabz	19	1000	1000	100	500	500	100	38,2	7,3	19,1
3	Kamashi	18	1500	900	60	750	450	60	0	0	0
4	The lamp	5	500	580	116	250	290	116	0	0	0
Жами		60	5000	4480	89,6	2500	2240	89,6	41,5	7,9	19,0

Only 89.6 percent of the plan was fulfilled. This mockery is explained by the fact that the area of planted land has decreased less than planned. Given that maxsar grain is procured through the separation of dye for production, we will analyze the volume of dyeing. In the reporting year, farms were paid 7.9 million soums. This accounted for 19.0 per cent of the total amount to be paid (of which only 1.8 per cent in Yakkabog and 19.1 per cent in Shakhrisabz) (Table 3). JSC "Kasan Oil-Extraction" has signed contracts with 51 farms for the cultivation of sunflower. Under these agreements, 1,140 hectares of land have actually been allocated to sunflower farms in the region. However, the area under sunflower is less than 260 hectares. However, due to the high yield, the gross yield of sunflower increased by 24.7%. Farms actually received 4.6 million soums from JSC "Kasan Oil Extraction". received a sum of money [29]. This is 98.5 percent less than the amount specified in the plan. Farms in Shakhrisabz, Kamashi, Kasbi and Kitab districts have not been paid at all.

Table 3.

Execution of the contract between Kashkadarya region JSC "Kason oil-extraction" and farmers for the cultivation of sunflower (2019)

№	Districts	Number of farms	Crop area, ga			Gross yield, t			Amount of bon, mln.sum		
			plan	truth	difference, (+-)	plan	truth	difference %	plan	truth	difference, (+-)
1	Yakkabog	8	200	230	+30,0	300	426	142,0	12,6	1,2	-11,4
2	Shahrisabz	5	150	200	+50,0	225	334,5	148,7	33,4	0	-33,4
3	Kamashi	7	100	86	-14,0	150	150	100,0	6,3	0	-6,3
4	Koson	12	250	214	-36,0	375	450	120,0	145	1,1	-143,9
5	Mirishkor	10	250	220	-30,0	240	375	100,0	44	1,2	-42,8
6	Muborak	7	200	150	-50,0	100	322,5	107,5	48,3	1,1	-47,2
7	Kasbi	1	250	20	-230,0	300	30	10,0	9,45	0	-9,45
8	Kitob	1	0	20	+20	0	20	0	3,15	0	-3,15
Total		51	1400	1140	-260	1690	2108	124,7	302,2	4,6	-297,6

We can see the same situation in the implementation of contracts for the supply of seeds of molasses. In particular, 35 farms operating in the regions have signed contracts with this enterprise, and farmers have delivered 0.275 tons of seeds. Although the plan was to deliver 2,175 tons of seeds, the contract was fulfilled only by 12.6%. Farmers were paid only 4.6 million soums, or only 1.5 percent of the planned amount. Farms in Kamashi, Chirakchi, Kasbi and Yakkabag districts did not receive seeds at all. This was due to the fact that farmers were not paid the initial fee. It should be noted that a relatively high rate in the region can be observed in Shakhrisabz (60% of the contract for the supply of seeds) and Mirishkor (40%) districts, but this can not be considered positive. (Table 4) [29].

Table 4.

Execution of the contract between JSC "Kasan Oil Extraction" Kashkadarya region and farmers for the supply of seeds of molasses (2019)

№ Districts	Number of farms	Seeds, tons			The amount of beans, mln. sum		
		plan	truth	difference,%	plan	truth	difference,%
1 Shahrisabz	4	0,1	0,06	60,0	12,6	1,2	9,5
2 Kamashi	5	0,05	0	0,0	33,4	0	0,0
3 The lamp	2	0,05	0	0,0	6,3	0	0,0
4 Koson	14	1,15	0,11	9,6	145	1,1	0,8
5 Mirishkor	4	0,15	0,06	40,0	44	1,2	2,7
6 Muborak	3	0,575	0,05	8,7	48,3	1,1	2,3
7 Kasbi	2	0,075	0	0,0	9,45	0	0,0
8 Yakkabog	1	0,025	0	0,0	3,15	0	0,0
Total:	35	2,175	0,275	12,6	302,19	4,6	1,5

Analyzing the volume of bonds, 389.2 mln. Instead of 150.5 million soums, the plant provided only 150.5 million soums to farms. UZS, ie the fulfillment of the contract was 38.7%. It should be noted that although a 100 per cent result was achieved in seed delivery in Yakkabog, only 15.6 per cent was paid to farms. In Kasan district, the largest number of farms (14) signed contracts, the contract for the supply of seeds was 41.1%, and the payment for seed was 84.8%. This indicates that there are problems and shortcomings between the enterprise and the farms that need to be addressed (Table 5) [29].

In general, such contractual relations and large losses in the activities of JSC "Kasan Oil-Extraction" and JSC "Karshi Oil-Extraction" in Kashkadarya region are a major obstacle to further expansion and development of enterprises. Reducing or optimizing such costs is critical to the prospects of businesses.

Table 5.

Implementation of the agreement between JSC "Kasan Oil-Extraction" Kashkadarya region and farmers on the cultivation of sunflower seeds (2019)

№	Districts	Number of farms	of Seeds, tons			The amount of beans, mln. sum		
			plan	truth	difference,%	plan	truth	difference,%
1	Shahrisabz	4	0,5	0,12	24,0	100	4,3	4,3
2	Kamashi	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	The lamp	2	0	0,09	0	12	1,9	15,8
4	Koson	14	0,9	0,37	41,1	151	128,0	84,8
5	Mirishkor	4	1,25	0,3	24,0	97	12,4	12,8
6	Muborak	3	0	0	0	4,2	0	0,0
7	Kasbi	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Yakkabog	1	0,18	0,18	100,0	25	3,9	15,6
Total:		35	2,83	1,06	37,5	389,2	150,5	38,7

Based on the results of scientific and methodological developments and economic analysis developed in the course of research, it should be noted that in general, the activities of economic entities involved in the cultivation, processing and sale of oilseeds incur significant costs, including contract costs, as well as raw materials. material losses are occurring. With this in mind, the problems and efficiency indicators of industrial enterprises processing cotton and oilseeds were studied. Taking into account the efficiency of raw cotton and oilseeds growers and industrial enterprises specializing in their processing in Kashkadarya region, 115 farmers growing raw cottonseeds and oilseeds in Kashkadarya region were surveyed in order to study the problems in their activities and eliminate future problems. farms, 25 dehkan farms and 12 agricultural enterprises, as well as oilseed processing enterprises "Kasan Oil Extraction" and "Karshi Oil Extraction" (business managers on behalf of the enterprises) took part in the survey and expressed their views and problems in the field. The 154 respondents surveyed surveyed the most important key issues in the cultivation and processing of oilseeds (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The results of a survey to study the problems in the activities of enterprises growing and processing oilseeds

132 or 85.7% of the respondents answered "no" to the question "Is there a contractual relationship in the supply of technical cotton seeds and other oilseeds?", 125 respondents or 81.2% said that it is necessary to increase the yield of oilseeds. 83 or 53.9% of the respondents answered "no" to the question "Are they provided with agricultural machinery and are innovative technologies used in the processing of products? answered "yes" to the question, 122 or 79.2% of the respondents answered "no" to the question "are the economic relations between the enterprises growing and processing oilseeds well established". Also, 135 or 87.7% of

respondents answered “yes” to the question “Is the supply of oilseeds by private individuals”, 91 or 59.1% of respondents answered “yes” The answer to the question "Is there enough agronomists?" The survey also asked whether "quality control" is applied to control the compliance of cottonseeds and other oilseeds with the requirements of the State Tax Committee, "whether the payments are made on time in accordance with the contracts between oilseeds and oilseeds." , “Are other types of crops grown on land intended for oilseeds” and other similar questions [30].

Conclusion

It is expedient to include the following in the main tasks of the Kashkadarya Regional Center for Support and Development of Oil and Gas Products:

- organization of constant communication with them in order to determine and analyze the development efficiency of oil extraction, infrastructure facilities;
- Organization of cooperation with seed research institutions, higher and secondary special education institutions specializing in agriculture and technology;
- organization of control over the implementation of the decisions of the Coordinating Council;
- Advising agro-cluster participants on technological, economic, organizational, legal and other issues;
- implementation of other activities related to ensuring the effective development of entities involved in agrocluster activities.

At the same time, the agro-cluster on oil and fat should create its own website in order to carry out its activities not only in the region, but also abroad, and place on this site all the necessary information for potential customers and consumers.

In addition, in the formation and development of oil and gas clusters, the regional government should provide appropriate assistance in the following areas: the organization of information support for the development of the cluster; ensuring the implementation of cluster programs aimed at increasing product competitiveness; promoting the formation of favorable economic conditions for further development of clusters.

As a result, due to the overall synergistic effect and the scale of production, the expansion of the product range leads primarily to the optimization of all organizational and economic processes in the chain of agricultural and food products from the field to the consumer, primarily in the form of regional brands. In addition, it is possible to expand the "coverage" of the regional cluster by expanding production, which will lead to new sales markets, which will lead to significant growth of the regional economy and the subsequent transformation of existing clusters into new more advanced clusters.

Foreign practice shows that the establishment of oil and gas clusters leads to a doubling of productivity in the cultivation and production of oilseeds.

To make full use of the potential of the oil and gas cluster, it is advisable to implement the following strategic, innovative measures:

- Formation of guaranteed oil production areas in Kashkadarya region on the basis of the introduction of innovative technologies in agriculture and the intensification of the development of selection and seed production, which will make the existing clusters one of the most important agro-clusters in Uzbekistan;
- Targeted development of the cluster by replenishment of the food chain by enterprises for deep processing of oilseeds, which will allow to export high value products;
- Encourage the development of cooperation and integration mechanisms between cluster participants through the development and implementation of subcontracting, public-private partnerships, including the "Kashkadarya brand" programs and the implementation of joint innovation-cluster investment projects with the support of state or regional authorities.

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